

Towards Credible Simulators: A Validation Methodology for Safety-Critical Virtual Testing

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Abstract. Recent advances in high-performance graphics and physics engines (e.g., Unreal Engine) have popularized simulators for safety-critical system testing, yet credible validation is essential for reliable outcomes. This paper introduces a novel methodology for validating simulation toolchains, combining principles from SAE and UNECE frameworks with validation cycles to accommodate evolving safety-critical requirements. We demonstrate this approach through a case study evaluating the colour fidelity of an Unreal Engine-based perception toolchain for safety-critical applications such as human and obstacle detection. Comparative tests of real and simulated camera outputs show that Unreal Engine's camera model achieves " ΔE " < 4 under controlled lighting, closely matching the reference colours, but complex real-world lighting and seasonal variations can introduce perceivable colour discrepancies. Our iterative methodology enables progressive refinements (reducing " ΔE " variations) and establishes critical traceability links for assessors related to evolving system requirements, toolchain modifications, as well as validation evidence. The resulting framework provides assessors with a verifiable chain of evidence from initial discrepancies to compliance, bridging the gap between adaptive development and certification needs.

Keywords: Simulation validation · Safety-critical systems · Virtual testing toolchain · Unreal engine · Camera model fidelity.

1 Introduction

The increasing complexity of automation in industries such as automotive and mobile machinery demands rigorous testing and validation to ensure safety, reliability, and performance. In particular, in the forestry domain, research and development are underway to automate tasks such as site preparation and planting [9] as well as the collection and transportation of logs securely using mobile machinery [11, 14] intended to operate in harsh and dynamic environments. Traditional testing and validation approaches using extensive field trials are often impractical for these machines due to logistical constraints, high costs, and the difficulty

in replicating diverse operational scenarios. As a result, simulation-based testing has emerged as a vital tool, offering a controlled and cost-effective platform to validate and test perception applications, decision-making algorithms, and autonomous functionalities [16].

High-performance graphics rendering engines, such as Unreal Engine [1], offer realistic modelling of environments and enable the development and testing of perception applications using virtual models of sensors such as camera and LiDAR under varying weather conditions, lighting, and terrain. Renowned simulators in the automotive sector, such as CARLA [7], utilize Unreal Engine’s capabilities to create immersive simulation environments, allowing researchers and developers to evaluate the performance of their algorithms in controlled yet diverse settings. Similarly, an Unreal Engine 5-based simulator [8] is currently being developed within an EU project called AGRARSENSE [4] to provide tailored simulations for forestry applications. However, to ensure credible virtual testing, these simulation tools must be rigorously validated to accurately replicate real-world phenomena such as sensor noise, lighting, and environmental effects. Without robust validation, they fail to establish the credibility needed to reliably represent operational scenarios for testing safety-critical applications.

While methods for ensuring the validity and credibility of simulation toolchains for virtual testing are advancing in the automotive domain, they are yet to be established for mobile machinery. For autonomous vehicle testing, SAE International has developed a comprehensive approach for validating virtual toolchains [10]. On the other hand, the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) has introduced the New Assessment/Test Method (NATM) [20], which provides a broader framework for credibility assessment of virtual testing toolchains for validating Automated Driving Systems (ADS), though it only briefly discusses the validation method from the SAE comprehensive approach. However, these existing methodologies generally assume static requirements, lacking the iterative validation cycles crucial for accommodating evolving requirements during safety-critical system development. Moreover, as ADS functionalities advance and safety standards are updated, simulation toolchains may need continuous refinements to accurately model sensor behaviours or incorporate additional environmental factors not originally considered.

This paper introduces a simulation toolchain validation methodology featuring iterative validation cycles, as illustrated in Fig. 1, to support assessor-verifiable traceability across requirement changes. To demonstrate this approach, we apply it to an Unreal Engine-based simulator for forestry applications to validate its camera model’s colour fidelity. Our focus on color fidelity is motivated by previous work [5] that systematically evaluated how color deviations affect YOLO object detection accuracy, particularly for safety-critical tasks like people detection. In this work, we evaluate the camera model’s colour accuracy with controlled laboratory tests, followed by scenario-based tests under real operating conditions. The case study demonstrates how iterative validation can bridge the gap between adaptive development processes and certification needs for safety-critical systems. While we validated the colour fidelity of the camera sensor in

Fig. 1: Overview of the broader credibility assessment workflow for virtual toolchains, where the validation stages derived from SAE & NATM frameworks are extended with the proposed iterative validation cycle to accommodate evolving requirements of safety-critical systems.

our case study, the proposed validation methodology itself is domain-agnostic and can be extended to other sensor modalities or system requirements. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- *Comprehensive validation methodology*: We present a simulation toolchain validation methodology featuring iterative validation cycles that maintain compliance evidence across requirement changes.
- *Case study on Unreal Engine camera-based perception*: We demonstrate our methodology by empirically evaluating the Unreal Engine camera model’s ability to replicate real-world colour accuracy using standardized metrics relevant for safety certification.
- *Open-source tools*: We provide a virtual lab asset¹ for Unreal Engine camera model validation and a Python-based tool² for processing sensor images with a ColorChecker target for quantitative colour accuracy measurements.

2 Related Work

Methods for validating simulation toolchains are crucial for ensuring their credibility and have been an active area of research for over two decades. As recently

¹ <https://github.com/RISE-Dependable-Transport-Systems/UE-Camera-Validation>

² <https://github.com/RISE-Dependable-Transport-Systems/ColorCheckerAnalysis>

surveyed in [6], an early foundational framework [3] include a three-step verification and validation (V&V) procedure [3] emphasize establishing face validity, conducting stress tests, and comparing simulation outputs against empirical data. Another surveyed approach [17] distinguishes between conceptualization and computerization, stressing that both verification (ensuring the correctness of the computer program) and validation (evaluating the accuracy of the model’s representation of the real system) are vital. Additionally, systematic procedures have been proposed that involve comparing model outputs with experimental data, extrapolating predictions, and assessing whether the model meets its intended application requirements [15].

Recent work in [19] explored methods for assessing the overall credibility of virtual testing environments, linking real-world and simulated scenarios through multivariate metrics and highlighting the need for holistic validation of automated driving functions. Furthermore, structured frameworks such as the SAE comprehensive approach [10] and the UNECE’s NATM [20] emphasize the importance of validating virtual testing toolchains. The SAE offers a three-phase comprehensive validation methodology detailing the model requirements definition, validation execution, and the usage of a validated virtual testing toolchain. On the other hand, the NATM presents a multi-pillar approach for ADS validation, where simulation/virtual testing plays a critical role in assessing the ADS functionalities. Specifically, Annex III of NATM mandates that the credibility of the modelling and simulation (M&S) toolchain must be established by rigorously assessing its technical accuracy, robustness, and documentation, including thorough code testing, V&V, calibration, and sensitivity analysis. Both these approaches highlight the need to quantitatively evaluate how well simulation models replicate real-world behaviours by validating subsystem models (such as environment, sensor, and vehicle models), sensor-vehicle interactions, and the full system integration within the simulation toolchain. While current validation approaches remain limited in handling continuous requirement updates during safety-critical system development, we propose an iterative validation approach, specifically addressing these unique challenges and evolving requirements in safety-critical systems.

3 Validation Methodology for Safety-Critical Simulations

In this section, we propose a validation methodology that builds upon the three established stages from validation frameworks such as SAE and NATM: toolchain requirements definition, subsystem model validation, and integrated system validation, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Our approach enhances these stages by introducing *iterative validation cycles* to address evolving requirements throughout both the system and toolchain lifecycles, along with a comprehensive *Toolchain Validation Report* to progressively document each validation activity throughout the validation process. This ensures that validation activities remain aligned with changes in operational context, regulatory standards, and system updates, while maintaining transparent traceability links that facilitate independent assessment

and regulatory certification. The proposed iterative validation cycle that applies to each validation activity in both subsystem and integrated validation stages, shown in Fig. 1, includes the following steps:

1. Initial validation against baseline requirements.
2. Documentation of validation activities and its results with a revision of the *Toolchain Validation Report*.
3. Exit if performance targets are acceptable or trigger requirement updates.
4. Targeted refinements due to evolved requirements.
5. Re-validation against updated requirements and return to step 2.

This cycle continues until acceptable performance is achieved or an informed decision is made to accept known limitations (which are then explicitly documented). Each iteration maintains links to the specific requirements being addressed, creating an auditable trail of progressive improvements that supports certification efforts even as requirements evolve. In the following, we describe how the three validation stages derived from the SAE and NATM frameworks are adapted to incorporate the proposed iterative cycle steps.

3.1 Toolchain Requirements Definition

The validation process begins with analyzing a thorough description of the operational context and intended use cases, ensuring that relevant aspects of the real-world environment, ranging from typical operating conditions to extreme edge cases, are considered. The outcome of this stage is a comprehensive set of requirements that explicitly allows evolution throughout both the toolchain’s lifecycle and that of the system under test (SUT), from early development to in-service deployment. This is achieved through *Requirement Version Control* with a formal change management process that documents the original baseline requirements and each subsequent requirement modification, including the rationale behind the change and the impact analysis on the validation status of affected components. Changes may be triggered by various factors, including new insights from in-service monitoring, updated regulatory standards, extensions of the ODD, etc. By explicitly linking these requirements to the safety-critical system’s intended use and operational context, this stage ensures that the simulation toolchain and the system development progress in tandem, with clear traceability between evolving requirements and validation evidence.

3.2 Subsystem Model Validation

With the toolchain requirements in place, this stage focuses on quantitative and qualitative assessments of individual modules such as sensor models, vehicle dynamics, and environmental interactions. *standalone* tests are performed, ensuring that the individual models meet their respective functional and performance requirements before being integrated into the larger system. For instance, the camera model is evaluated using standardized colour charts (e.g., Macbeth

ColorChecker) to measure colour accuracy under controlled lighting conditions. Each subsystem undergoes the iterative validation cycle described above, with the *Toolchain Validation Report* updated to include detailed documentation of standalone test procedures, results, identified discrepancies, and implemented refinements. This stage ensures that each component is robust enough to support the safety-critical functions of the overall system.

3.3 Integrated System Validation

In this stage, the individually validated subsystems are integrated successively, with validation performed after each addition until the complete simulation toolchain is fully integrated and evaluated. Each integration step is subjected to a series of dynamic scenarios that encompass both nominal and extreme operational conditions to simulate real-world events such as variable lighting, sudden environmental changes, and complex interactions among sensors, vehicle dynamics, and control systems. The iterative validation cycle is applied at each integration step, where the *Toolchain Validation Report* is continuously updated, documenting how emergent system-level properties either satisfy requirements or trigger refinement cycles that may propagate back to individual subsystems. This stage provides critical evidence of system-level compliance.

4 Validation of Colour Fidelity in Simulations for Testing Safety-Critical Object Detection Applications

This section demonstrates the practical application of our proposed iterative validation methodology for simulation toolchains. We present a case study focused on validating colour fidelity in camera-based perception simulations using an Unreal Engine 5-based simulator [8] developed within the AGRARSENSE EU project [4] for forestry applications. This case study illustrates how the proposed validation methodology systematically identifies discrepancies, triggers requirement and toolchain refinements, and maintains traceability.

4.1 Toolchain Requirements Definition

Beginning with our methodology’s first stage, we establish the baseline requirements for the simulation toolchain. The requirements are managed through a rigorous version control approach, capturing the evolution of specifications throughout the toolchain development and validation process. Table 1 outlines the contextual information for the case study in terms of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) and the Performance Metrics (PM). The ODD specification (ODD1–ODD2) defines the environmental conditions the toolchain must support and sets the scope for the toolchain requirements. The test scenarios are designed to evaluate the camera model’s colour fidelity in diverse weather conditions and under varying light colour temperatures. The PM specification (PM1) sets quantitative benchmarks for colour fidelity, derived from [5], corresponding

Table 1: ODD and PM specifications used as context for the case study

ID	Context Description	Acceptance Criteria
ODD1	Operate within an ODD featuring dynamic daytime lighting and variable weather (cloud cover, fog).	Sun elevation: -90° - 90° , Cloud cover: 0-100%, Fog density: 0-1
ODD2	Simulate colour temperature variations based on sun position.	2500K-7500K
PM1	Meet performance benchmark for colour fidelity throughout the ODD.	$\Delta E < 10$

Table 2: Toolchain requirements for the case study

ID	Requirement Description	Acceptance Criteria
FR1	Simulate sensor with high color fidelity in a representative laboratory setting.	$\Delta E < 5$
FR2	Render diverse terrain and realistic vegetation as specified in ODD.	Subjective score $\geq 8/10$
NFR1	Support high-resolution visual outputs.	12MP resolution

to an acceptable loss in precision of 8% by worst-case YOLO model. In this work, we use the industry standard "Delta E" metric [18] (denoted as ΔE in the following), which quantifies the perceptual difference between two colours, with lower values indicating higher fidelity. Table 2 further presents a non-exhaustive set of traceable requirements for the simulation toolchain. The Functional Requirements (FR1–FR2) specify the simulation objectives for sensor model accuracy (derived from [5] for an acceptable detection precision loss of 2%) and environmental realism. Finally, the Non-Functional Requirement (NFR1) ensures that the toolchain delivers high-resolution images.

4.2 Subsystem Model Validation

In the next stage, the camera model validation experiments were conducted in a controlled lab environment, both physically and virtually, to compare the performance of the real and simulated camera systems under identical conditions. To match the real-world lab setup, a virtual lab asset³ was developed in the simulator, as shown in Fig. 2. For the real-world experiments, we used a Luxonis OAK-D Pro W camera [12], which was mounted on a tripod. This camera features a 12MP RGB sensor with a 4056x3040 resolution and a 95° horizontal field of view (FoV). The virtual camera’s FoV, pixel resolution, and aperture were configured to match the real camera. Two LED soft lights with rectangular panels were used to provide controlled lighting. These lights offer adjustable colour temperatures within the range from 3200K to 5400K accurately. The intensity and colour of these lights were measured during the tests using a Sekonic C-800 spectrometer and are used for configuring the virtual lights in the simulator.

For assessing the colour fidelity, we use the Macbeth Colour chart [13] printed on high-quality matte paper at a professional printing house to ensure colour fidelity and precise detail. During the tests, soft lights were positioned on

³ <https://github.com/RISE-Dependable-Transport-Systems/UE-Camera-Validation>

Fig. 2: Overview of the camera validation setup in the simulator.

each side of the chart at around a 45° angle to minimize shadows and ensure even illumination of the test charts. At a fixed distance of 1 m, with the test chart centred in the camera’s field of view, as shown in Fig. 2, camera outputs are captured while varying the colour temperature from 3500K to 5000K in increments of 500K. To maintain consistent brightness across tests, auto exposure was enabled on both the real and virtual cameras during testing. The real camera utilizes the OAK-D’s built-in auto-exposure algorithm, while the simulator employs Unreal Engine’s histogram-based auto-exposure functionality.

Given that white balancing (WB) plays a critical role in achieving colour fidelity, we conducted real-world tests by capturing images using both the OAK-D camera’s auto WB algorithm and manual WB (set to match the light source colour temperature measured with the spectrometer). In the simulations, images were captured by matching the light source temperature directly, simulating manual WB. Fig. 3 shows a sample side-by-side comparison of the real and virtual camera outputs. To compute ΔE , we developed a Python-based application⁴ featuring a graphical user interface (GUI) that automatically detects the 24 patches in the Macbeth Color chart and computes ΔE values. Figure 4 compares the colour fidelity of real and virtual cameras measured in terms of ΔE under different light source temperatures.

In the real-world tests, while the OAK-D camera’s auto WB algorithm produced consistent ΔE values across tested temperatures, it generally yielded higher ΔE than the manual WB setting (which was matched to the spectrometer-measured light source temperature), except at 4000K. This anomaly can be attributed to the characteristic blue spike in the spectral power distribution (SPD) of the LED light source, shown in Fig. 5, a known limitation of LED lights [2]. When using manual WB set to the nominal temperature of this non-ideal light source, the OAK-D camera’s fixed gain adjustments (likely optimized

⁴ <https://github.com/RISE-Dependable-Transport-Systems/ColorCheckerAnalysis>

Fig. 3: Illustration of real and virtual camera outputs in a laboratory setup under 5000K lighting with the WB manually set to 5000K.

Fig. 4: Comparison of real and virtual camera performance in terms of the colour accuracy (ΔE) at varying light temperatures.

for a smooth black-body spectrum) failed to account for the excess blue light, with this effect particularly amplified at 4000K due to the unique intensity and spectral position (450-460nm) of the blue spike.

Typically, ΔE values below 1 are imperceptible, values between 1 and 2 are noticeable only upon close inspection, and values between 2 and 10 are perceptible at a glance, with higher values indicating more substantial differences. In these tests, the virtual camera achieved ΔE values between 2.56 and 3.36. In contrast, the real camera with manual WB produced a wider range of ΔE values (from 5.10 at 5000K to 10.88 at 4000K), due to the impact of the non-ideal LED light source. Overall, the virtual camera, manually configured to match the light source temperature in simulations, consistently produced significantly lower ΔE values. Within the context of this case study involving an outdoor daytime environment without artificial lighting, it may not be essential to accurately replicate the LED blue spike characteristic. While this specific finding does not trigger a model requirement update, it is documented in the toolchain validation report. For future simulations involving artificial lighting, this documented observation would lead to targeted toolchain refinements.

Fig. 5: Observed spectral power distribution (SPD) of the LED light source at 4000K with the characteristic blue spike.

4.3 Integrated System Validation

The next step in our methodology involves integrating the camera into the virtual forest environment and examining its performance under representative outdoor scenarios. This integrated validation assesses whether the camera-environment interplay meets the requirements outlined earlier, particularly concerning lighting changes and weather variations relevant to safety-critical forestry tasks. To assess the integrated camera-environment system, we repeated color fidelity tests in the virtual world using the ColorChecker chart under four seasonal conditions (autumn, spring, summer, and winter), each incorporating varying cloud coverage and fog settings. For real-world comparisons, an accurate digital twin of an existing forest location in Umeå, Sweden, has been modelled in the simulator. In a scenario with cloudy but dry autumn conditions, we collected real-world data by capturing images of the ColorChecker chart using the OAK-D camera with auto WB. Additionally, spectrometer data were recorded to accurately quantify the lighting conditions. Figure 6 shows a side-by-side comparison of camera outputs across different seasonal conditions. In the autumn test, the real camera achieved a ΔE of 7.06, whereas the virtual camera produced ΔE values around 10.67. Notably, the real-world autumn environment appears more similar to the virtual summer than the virtual autumn simulation. In the other three seasonal scenarios, the virtual camera generally produced images with lower ΔE values (ranging from about 7.21 to 7.85).

Although the standalone validation provided key insights into sensor behaviour, the integrated tests revealed a mismatch between real-world and simulated autumn conditions, largely due to the simulator’s limitation in emulating leaf shedding and non-uniform seasonal leaf colouration. In response to these findings, we introduced a new functional requirement, FR3: “Support user-configurable leaf colour variations”. This targeted refinement, which significantly enhanced the simulator’s capability to represent seasonal variations, was validated through a qualitative assessment methodology comparing real-world and simulated autumn images in the digital twin of the forestry site. These iterative validation activities were comprehensively documented in a revised *Toolchain*

(a) Real autumn (b) Virtual autumn (c) Virtual summer (d) Virtual winter

Fig. 6: Comparison of camera outputs across seasons during scenario-based tests.

Validation Report, which demonstrated a substantial reduction in visual discrepancies between the real-world and virtual environment models.

5 Conclusion

This paper introduced a comprehensive iterative validation methodology for simulation toolchains intended for safety-critical applications, specifically addressing the challenges of evolving requirements and continuous development cycles. Through its three-stage approach encompassing toolchain requirements definition, subsystem model validation, and integrated system validation, our methodology establishes a robust framework that bridges the gap between adaptive development processes and certification needs. By applying this methodology to a case study evaluating the colour fidelity of Unreal Engine’s camera model, we demonstrated the practical effectiveness of our approach.

The standalone validation of the camera model under controlled laboratory conditions revealed that the virtual camera achieved promising colour accuracy (ΔE ranging from 2.56 to 3.36) when configured with ideal lighting parameters. However, real-world tests highlighted the impact of non-ideal light sources, motivating the need for use-case-specific refinements. Subsequent integrated system validation tests revealed important limitations, particularly in autumn environmental rendering, where discrepancies between real and virtual conditions triggered necessary vegetation model refinements. The iterative validation cycles proved essential in addressing these discrepancies while maintaining complete traceability. The methodology’s emphasis on version control, requirement evolution tracking, and progressive toolchain updates through the Toolchain Validation Report creates a verifiable chain of evidence crucial for safety certification.

While our demonstration focused on camera colour fidelity, the methodology’s domain-agnostic nature makes it applicable to other sensor modalities and system requirements. Moreover, the open-source tools developed, including a virtual lab environment and colour fidelity analysis tool, provide practical resources for the community to replicate and extend this work.

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